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THE ROLE OF SELF-EFFICACY, SELF-REGULATION, AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF EVIDENCE-BASED STRATEGIES FOR ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING

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INTRODUCTION

The primary objective of this investigation is to explore the relationships between self-efficacy, self-regulation, and English proficiency among senior high school students attending public and private schools in Tarlac. The research endeavors to elucidate how these psychological constructs influence academic performance in English language acquisition, with the objective of developing evidence-based strategies to support students in navigating academic challenges. These strategies are designed to equip teachers to better address self-efficacy and self-regulation in their teaching. More specifically, this paper examines how evidence-based strategies can be designed and applied to strengthen self-efficacy and self-regulation in English language learning (ELL). By integrating psychological theory with classroom practice, it offers a framework to help curriculum developers, teachers, and students build a more effective and empowering ELL and fostering an improved academic outcome while supporting the holistic development of students' linguistic abilities.

Statement of the Problem

This research intends to address the following questions:

1. How may the self-efficacy of the respondents be described, specifically in learning the English language?
2. How may the self-regulation in English language learning of the respondents be described?
3. How may the English academic performance of senior high school students in Tarlac be described in terms of:
 - 3.1 Academic performance in English,
 - 3.2 Participation in English extra-curricular activities
4. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' self-efficacy and their academic performance in English?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' self-regulation and their academic performance in English?
6. What evidence-based strategies can be developed and implemented to enhance self-efficacy and self-regulation, thereby helping students navigate academic challenges?

Hypothesis

Ho: There is no significant relationship between self-efficacy (SE) and English academic performance (EAP).

Ho: There is no significant relationship between self-regulation (SR) and English academic performance (EAP).

This study included senior high school learners attending various public and private institutions across the towns of Capas, Bambang, and Concepcion, Tarlac. Representative from public schools in this study included Dapdap High School, Santa Rosa National High School, and Cristo Rey National High School. Meanwhile, for private institutions, the study selected Sto. Niño Academy, Well Spring Senior High School, Inc, and Good Shepherd Christian School. Based on the data gathered from the Learner Information System (LIS) of the selected schools, there were 3,001 students enrolled in the Senior High School across six institutions. The sample size was calculated using Slovin's formula, with a total sample size of 353.

A self-constructed questionnaire served as the primary research instrument in this study, designed to gather quantitative data regarding the connections among self-efficacy beliefs, self-regulated learning, and academic performance in senior high school students. The questionnaire consisted of 31 items divided into five sections. A five-point Likert scale was used in Section 1.1 and Section 1.2 to measure their responses, ranging from (1 - Strongly Disagree to 5 - Strongly Agree), with intermediate options including (2 - Disagree, 3 - Neutral, and 4 - Agree.) A frequency-based Likert scale was employed in Section 1.4. The final section involved collecting the respondents' third-quarter grades in the English subject to serve as a measure of their academic performance.

To establish the content validity of the questionnaires, three experts in the field reviewed and validated the tool. Their suggestions and recommendations were thoroughly considered and integrated into the final version of the instrument.

METHODS

The researcher personally distributed and explained the questionnaires to ensure that participants clearly understood the instructions. Sufficient time of 20 to 30 minutes was allotted for the completion of the survey. The academic records were securely stored and kept confidential throughout the research process. The acquired empirical data underwent a comprehensive analytical procedure employing both descriptive and inferential statistical methodologies to address the formulated research inquiries. The weighted mean was computed and described verbally.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

To analyze the levels of self-efficacy and self-regulation of the respondents, data were systematically organized and discussed according to the key variables of the study, providing a clear and coherent understanding of the findings.

1. The Respondents' Self-Efficacy in English Language Learning

The participants in this study generally possess high levels of self-efficacy in learning the English language, as indicated by an aggregated mean of **3.69**. Notably, the respondents demonstrated the highest self-efficacy in aspects influenced by vicarious experiences and peer support, while scoring lower in areas of anxiety management and maintaining confidence when receiving negative feedback. These findings align strongly with Albert Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory, a framework positing that self-efficacy beliefs are significantly impacted by mastery experiences, vicarious learning, social persuasion, and physiological and affective states in shaping self-efficacy beliefs.

2. The Respondents Self-Regulation in English Language Learning

Senior High school students' self-regulation mean is rated high which is indicative of proactive and strategic approaches to language learning. **The data indicates that learners demonstrate a**

generally elevated degree of self-regulation in their English language learning as reflected by an overall mean score of 3.73, which suggests that they typically engage in proactive, strategic, and reflective behaviors that support their language acquisition. Paying attention to mistakes and learning from them and persisting in improving English despite setbacks obtained the highest regulatory behavior.

3. English Academic Performance of Senior High School Students

The third quarter academic grades of Grade 11 and Grade 12 students in *Reading and Writing Skills* and *Creative-Non Fiction* subjects, respectively, is characterized by an average grade of 88.79. These statistics results indicate a performance level that surpasses the average benchmark. Consequently, this data suggests that, on average, senior high school learners in Tarlac demonstrate an above-average level in English proficiency during the third quarter.

4. The relationship between Self- efficacy (SE) and English academic performance (EAP)

There is a moderate positive relationship between senior high school students' self-efficacy and academic performance with a Pearson correlation coefficient of $r = 0.56$. This significant relationship emphasized that as the respondents' confidence level to accomplish task in English increases, the higher English academic performance they can attain.

5. The Significant Relationship of Self-Regulation (SR) to English Academic Performance (EAP)

There is a significant relationship between senior high school students' self-regulation and academic performance. The analysis revealed a statistically significant and moderately positive relationship between the two variables, with a Pearson correlation coefficient of $r = 0.52$. This finding indicates that as students' self-regulation skills increase, their English academic performance also tends to improve.

6. Evidence-Based Strategies for Enhancing Self-efficacy and Self-Regulation

A. Strategies for Enhancing Self-Efficacy in English Language Learning

The goal of these strategies is to cultivate student confidence, resilience, and a positive self-perception regarding their English language capabilities.

1. **"Success Ladders"** serve as an effective tool for fostering mastery experiences in the classroom. Teachers play a key role by breaking down complex tasks into manageable parts, while curriculum developers design structured learning progressions that build upon prior knowledge. By integrating scaffolding into achievable tasks, Success Ladders exemplify how mastery experiences can be intentionally embedded into instruction to strengthen students' self-efficacy.
2. **"Peer Showcase & Share"** is an effective classroom strategy designed to promote vicarious experiences through peer observation. This structured interaction allows learners to witness successful English language use among their classmates, reinforcing the belief that they, too, can achieve similar success.
3. **"Two Stars and a Wish"** is a classroom feedback strategy that exemplifies verbal persuasion by combining two specific positive comments with one constructive suggestion. This method promotes a growth mindset by framing feedback in an encouraging, balanced way that highlights students' effort and progress rather than focusing solely on errors.
4. **"Error Analysis Journal"** is a reflective strategy that helps students transform their English language mistakes into opportunities for learning and growth. By recording their errors, analyzing the causes,

and planning how to improve, students begin to view mistakes not as failures but as essential parts of the learning process.

B. Strategies for Enhancing Self-Regulation in English Language Learning

The strategies for fostering self-regulated learning are grounded in Barry Zimmerman's (2000) model, which portrays learners as active agents in their own learning. These approaches aim to empower students with the necessary skills to take control of and guide their own language learning process effectively.

1. **"SMART English Goal Workshop"** is an instructional strategy designed to help students set clear, achievable objectives by using the SMART framework—Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-bound. Through this guided activity, teachers support learners in transforming vague intentions into concrete goals.
2. **"The Pomodoro Technique"** is a practical classroom strategy that supports students during the active phase of learning by promoting focused, sustained effort. Using a timer, students work in 25-minute intervals of uninterrupted concentration followed by short breaks. This method helps address a common challenge—managing distractions—by training students to regulate their attention and build concentration stamina.
3. **"Error Analysis Portfolio"** is a reflective tool designed to support the final phase of self-regulation, where students evaluate their performance and emotional responses. In this activity, students compile samples of their own English work that contain errors. For each error, they identify the type, analyze its possible cause, and apply a targeted correction strategy. This approach moves beyond basic error correction, encouraging deeper metacognitive reflection and strategic adjustment.

By integrating these evidence-based strategies in English language learning curriculum, teachers can systematically enhance students' self-efficacy, making them more confident and resilient, while simultaneously strengthening their self-regulation abilities.

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